

Clinical Image: surgery under battery operated headlights

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Surgery needs electricity. Dependable power supplies are a major problem in the Global South. Diesel generators, when available, provide a heavily polluting alternative. This image shows Dr. Philip Alexander operating in Kaaza, Spiti Valley, Himachal Pradesh, India, using a battery-operated camping headlight, theatre lights powered with a car battery, and diathermy powered by a diesel generator. Clean, reliable energy that will improve patient outcomes and simultaneously protect the local environment is a priority for hospitals in low and middle income countries.

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